

McKinsey
& Company

Project report

Future Circular Collider

24/7 Clean Energy Supply

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Introduction

The international Future Circular Collider study is analyzing the feasibility of a 90 to 100 km long circular infrastructure to host first a lepton particle collider (FCC-ee) and then a hadron particle collider (FCC-hh). The scientific research program is foreseen to start with the first machine around 2045. Sustainability, societal impact potentials and environmental compatibility are key topics that the study addresses from the beginning onwards. This report provides the results of a first, exploratory study that aimed to understand how and under which conditions such a research infrastructure can be powered with renewable energy sources.

Today, CERN's infrastructures and research instruments consume between 1.0 and 1.3 TWh of electricity per year. It will reach 1.6 TWh around 2029 with the upgrade of the LHC experiments, the HL-LHC and a new data center. In the context of the energy transition and rising energy costs, one of the questions to answer is what a sustainable and affordable power source for an FCC could look like. This document summarises the outcomes of that exploratory study in the following chapters:

1. Power needs with an FCC
2. Objectives for the FCC era power procurement
3. The solution: Offshore wind in France, procured via PPA pre-FID
 - 3.1. Technology mix
 - 3.2. Procurement options
 - 3.3. Location options
4. Societal impacts
5. Next steps

All energy cost estimates in this report are excluding taxes as well as transmission & distribution charges. Transmission & distribution charges would depend on the type of connection used for the FCC. Under today's tariffs in France, assuming HTB3 type connection, transmission and distribution charges would be around 10 EUR/MWh.

1 Power needs for the FCC era

The Future circular collider lepton collider (FCC-ee) has an electricity consumption during beam operation between 1.3 and 2.0 TWh per year depending on the physics program. CERN's total energy needs during the FCC-ee era with the operation of other physics research facilities such as the SPS north area and all Meyrin site would vary between 0.5 TWh and 2.6 TWh depending on the choice of the operated facilities. The peak consumption would not exceed 2.6 TWh during the FCC-ee ttbar operation mode around 2055.

During operation, the FCC-ee will account for about 70% of CERN's total energy need. During the construction period, the FCC will require around 200 to 600 GWh of electricity per year. The average annual energy need of the FCC-ee during its lifetime is around 1.5 TWh.

Figure 1 CERN's total expected annual power needs during the FCC era. The FCC needs are represented in dark blue color.

The energy supply will need to adapt to the FCC's dynamic power consumption needs within the year and from one hour to another:

Each year, there will be an approximately 4-month long maintenance period during which energy consumption will be significantly lower than during operation. Today, this period is assumed to be in the cold season, when, historically, energy prices are higher. During the maintenance period, the total maximum load is expected to be between 65 and 78 MW¹.

During beam operation, when physics research is being performed, the total load would be between 237 MW and 387 MW, depending on the operation mode (Z, W, H, ttbar) – except for a few days in-between, when technical breaks will reduce the total demand need to 82-112 MW¹. During beam operations, power will vary significantly by up to 150 MW from one hour to the next. While ramping up to maximum load can be planned, load can drop by 150 MW within about 300 μs in the

¹ Depending on the type of operations (e.g., Z, W, H, TT)

event of faults and when the beam is sent to the dump. This rapid change of power will be smooth thanks to local energy storage. Once standby mode is entered, the machine remains in this mode until the root cause of the fault is identified and remedied. Shifting load on short-term notice (e.g., a few hours ahead) is an option but it would require investments (e.g., storage), has technical limits, and it would require much effort to replan energy demand and FCC activities (e.g., physicists would require about one week visibility on when they can perform experiments).

2 Objectives for the FCC era power procurement

Three objectives for power procurement were identified during this study:

1. **CERN aspires to supply FCC with “green power”**. The study focuses on the feasibility to supply the FCC with renewable energy sources as much as possible. The solutions considered are creating additional Renewable Energy Sources (RES) capacities – and, potentially, storage, to avoid being supplied with other forms of energy such as gas/coal power from the grid or at least to be able to compensate for the use of other power sources, including decarbonized but not renewable energy during hours when RES production is below need.
2. **CERN would like to secure affordable power supply** for the FCC-ee operation period from 2045 to 2059. Power procured at cost plus margin can be made possible by providing long-term revenue security to owners via Purchase Price Agreements (PPA) and/or own investment. In this case, CERN would have to be willing to pay a premium to avoid intermittency and to mitigate profile risks.
3. **CERN aims to limit energy costs uncertainties** to about 20 – 30% variation on a year over year basis, ideally secured on a long-term horizon covering the 15 years FCC-ee operation phase to be able to manage the budget.

Security of supply would be guaranteed through connection to the national high-voltage grid. The study of such connection was out of scope of this study.

3 The solution: Offshore wind in France, procured via PPA pre-FID

Offshore wind has been identified as a key technology for CERN for electricity supply, to be procured “investment-alike” via a PPA pre-FID supporting the development of a new offshore wind park located in France, with a partner who makes the capital investment and carries the construction & operational risks. CERN would enable the construction of an offshore wind farm larger than its needs for the FCC-ee (such as a 1 GW project for approximately a need between 230 MW and 380 MW² for the FCC-ee).

The energy cost (pure electricity cost excluding taxes, transmission and distribution costs) for CERN is estimated to be between 43 and 78 EUR/MWh³ – a range accounting for uncertainties in Capex and market price – in real economic terms of today (2023). This cost includes the sourcing price of PPAs, and adjustments needed on the grid to match CERN’s profile. This could be a very attractive energy price and would reduce financial risk substantially.

Each year, CERN would buy from the offshore wind project at least the total amount of power required. However, buying from the grid would still be necessary in some hours when CERN’s demand is higher than the contracted renewable power production. This is more likely to be during more expensive hours (i.e., when overall renewable power production is low). Similarly, selling to the grid would be required in other hours when CERN’s demand is lower than the contracted renewable power production. This is more likely to be during hours when market prices are the lowest (i.e., when overall renewable power production is high). These risks, called profile risks, could be managed by a 3rd party or the PPA provider.

Figure 2 Build-up of energy costs

² As each year is expected to have a different volume need during the FCC-ee operation.

³ Note that this estimation does not include adjustments for inflation.

3.1 TECHNOLOGY MIX

Based on cost assumptions and the expected hourly load profile of CERN, a linear optimization was done to identify the cost-optimal technology mix – assuming the RES portfolio would generate at least the energy required by CERN on a yearly basis in various scenarios.

Offshore wind has been identified as the optimal power source from among intermittent RES (solar PV, onshore wind, offshore wind).

- **Cost-competitive:** For the 2045 horizon, offshore wind appears to be more cost-competitive for the target profile than onshore wind, solar. Offshore wind turbines are larger, offshore wind farms have higher capacity and a higher load factor (the actual power generated divided by the theoretical maximum power production) than other RES and they do not contend with land scarcity (e.g., the ZAN⁴ law in France and the SdA⁵ regulation in Switzerland). In the basic setup considering electricity supply from off-shore wind sources only, energy costs would be in the 43 to 78 EUR/MWh range with about 60% of hourly matching⁶.
- **Lower supply risk:** Offshore wind is considered a lower supply risk technology as it is characterized by a more stable production profile and it is more likely than other RES to produce power during hours when the market is short on power.
- **Simpler procurement:** Considering the size of typical state-of-the-art offshore wind farms in the GW range, only one or a few contracts would be needed to secure CERN's total energy need compared to signing 20+ PPAs with various onshore wind and solar PPA providers. This simplifies the procurement thereof.
- **CERN would be an attractive partner for offshore wind developers** in the context of the current allocation of seabed in France, mainly for two reasons:
 - The ability to contract well in advance of the commission date (typically 8 years before a windfarm begins to supply energy) would help offshore developers to come to a financial closure and secure attractive debt financing.
 - CERN, due to its reputation, would help developers get priority to obtain seabed to build offshore wind parks. Seabed could be an in-kind contribution to the developer providing that power would need to be contracted with CERN (at least up to CERN's need). Such contribution has to be accounted for in a lowered PPA price (i.e. the associated cost have to be excluded from the asset costs) to reflect the need of selecting the lowest compliant bid.

Offshore wind as power source would require buying missing and selling excess energy on the grid throughout the year – a common practice in the industry today – as the offshore wind generation profile will be different from CERN's required load (for instance selling 0.7 TWh and buying 0.7 TWh out of 1.7 TWh during different times in 2045). In total, during the 15 years of FCC-ee operations this could sum-up

⁴ "Zéro Artificialisation Nette"

⁵ "Surface d'assolement"

⁶ % of RES production that is used to meet the demand directly or through storage system alone, i.e. not sold back on the grid.

to approximately 12 TWh⁷ to be bought from the grid and 12 TWh to be sold to the grid.

CERN could further increase the level of hourly matching from 60% to 80% or 95% by **adding solar PV, onshore wind** capacities (which would be more economical than simply adding more capacity from offshore wind to achieve the same level of hourly matching) and it would have the following implications:

- Increasing energy costs by 7 EUR/MWh to reach 80% with a target electricity cost of 50 EUR/MWh (price variability reduces due to supply certainty and significantly reduced market exposure) and
- increasing financial risks, but also lead to additional societal benefits as it will lead to overcapacity. CERN would receive more energy from the RES projects in total through a year and thus the amount of energy to be bought from and sold back to the grid increases (from 1.4 TWh in the base case to 1.5 TWh when reaching 80% and to 4 TWh when reaching 95%). This increases exposure to the wholesale market and the associated financial risk that market price could fall below the agreed PPA price at certain hours.

Raising supply RES supply coverage to 95% is possible today but is linked to the need to improve hourly matching and increase cost by 38 EUR/MWh.

Additionally, **contract (hybrid PPA) or deploy storage capacity** (battery, that can typically store power for 2 to 6 hours, and other innovative long-duration energy storage that could store energy beyond 6 hours and up to approximately a week) could have several advantages:

- Reducing further financial risk for CERN by reducing the need to purchase electricity from the market during low-supply periods,
- Making the electricity supply even more sustainable by increasing the actual level of renewables in the supply mix,
- Incentivizing investments into new technologies needed for the energy transition requiring not only green energy production but also flexible green energy,
- Potentially further reducing energy costs by using energy from storage instead of from the grid when market prices are higher:
 - Battery storage with a capacity of about 200 MW would slightly increase the RES matching level from 60% to 65% and would slightly reduce energy costs by about 2 EUR per MWh to 42 EUR/MWh for 60% coverage and to 48 EUR/MWh for 80% coverage.
 - Options with higher impacts are Long Duration Energy Storage (LDES) technologies (e.g., flow batteries or thermal storage). These could offer up to one week of storage – and, as these technologies are still in development, they could continue to become significantly more effective and affordable until 2035. Following this route could potentially raise the RES matching level to 95% in a more cost-effective way: reaching 95% *with* the storage solution would cost about 15 EUR/MWh less than reaching 95% *without* the storage solution, i.e. with a target price of 66 EUR/MWh.

⁷ Assuming that each year the volume secured through the PPA(s) is equal to the total need

Load shifting was studied to potentially adapt the yearly schedule (e.g., changing the long maintenance break from winter to summer) and adapt the timing of beam operation during the day.

- Shifting the beam operation period to the winter season would increase the hourly RES matching based on offshore wind alone from 60% to 70%, but it would also increase energy cost by about 10 EUR/MWh. This option would be worth exploring if gains from providing recovered waste heat to consumers with main needs during winter can compensate the increase in power cost. Breakeven would be reached if the provided waste-heat market value reaches about 20 million EUR per year, excluding additional investments required by heat suppliers and public energy supply agencies to provide the heat. A dedicated integrating cost study is required to reveal the best matching and cost optimisation of beam operation to seasonal RES electricity supply.
- Adapting the beam operation during the day – for example, adjusting the start and end times of physics operation would only lead to a minor cost advantage of about 1 EUR/MWh, representing a gain of about 2 million EUR per year.

Technical feasibility and investment cost and trade-off vs. the potential benefits of storage and load flexibility need to be further studied (e.g., storage could enable further optimization that have not been sized and could further reduce the energy cost for CERN, choice of storage technology would impact cost and benefits).

3.2 PROCUREMENT OPTIONS

Several procurement options were studied. Aiming for a main supply from offshore wind and no particular requirement to achieve immediately a very high hourly RES coverage, all options involve a single, large transaction to secure the base supply needs (further increasing hourly RES coverage may either include additional supply demand within the single transaction or further PPAs):

1. **Procurement of PPAs with equity participation**, where CERN would be a co-investor and an off-taker through a PPA "at-cost". This would result in securing power supply over a very long term at a lower price (4 EUR/MWh less than contracting a PPA without being an investor). While CERN would not build nor operate the RES project, CERN would bear some construction and operational risk as an investor.
2. **Procurement through a base pre-FID PPA and a series of additional PPAs** linked to individual RES projects. CERN could then build the desired portfolio but would bear profile risks. By contracting pre-FID, it would enable a cost+ pricing⁸ which is more attractive cost than contracting post-FID.
3. **Procurement of PPAs through an intermediary**, where CERN would benefit from a "full service" contract with a single party, who builds and manages the RES portfolio and manages the profile risk for CERN at a premium (about 5 to 10 EUR/MWh more than directly contracting a series of PPAs). This option is typically available from a limited set of large and diversified suppliers.

⁸ Pricing based on costs (e.g., capex and opex required to build the offshore wind farm) as opposed as based on value or alternative options for the buyer (e.g., linked to the market prices)

Depending on the procurement approach, energy cost would vary

Figure 3 Impact of procurement approach on energy costs

The most suitable procurement option for CERN is option 2: PPA(s) pre-FID with partnership(s), to enable the financing and secure the seabed(s). CERN would benefit from advantageous power prices, as it would make project development possible by:

- Securing long-term revenues for the developer before the financial closure of the project – a process so long that, for many potential off-takes, eight years can pass before the first generation of power is possible
- Procuring an advantage in securing the seabed, thanks to CERN's reputation and engagement to construct and operate a large research infrastructure with guaranteed long-term energy needs that represent a secured revenue for the supplier.

Alternatively, option 3 – procuring through an intermediary managing PPA portfolio and profile risks – could be considered to reduce financial uncertainties. Investing directly in a project – option 1 – is not recommended due to the construction and operational risks that CERN would bear in that case.

A PPA in the range of 15 years for the duration of the envisioned FCC-ee operation should be targeted. Contracts for a longer period do not lead to potentially lower costs, since a significant part of the RES project value can be secured through the initial 15 years. Contracts for a significantly shorter period would lead to not covering the entire envisioned FCC-ee operation period and potentially higher costs as financial security of the project would be reduced compared to a 15-year PPA.

3.3 LOCATION OPTIONS

France has been identified as the most suitable location to source green power for CERN, for the following reasons:

- **Attractive offshore potential:** The territory is well-suitable for offshore wind and is so far underdeveloped: it has the 2nd largest wind potential in Europe, after the UK, but with only less than 0.1 GW of installed capacity in 2022.
- **Government support:** Today, the French government supports the development of offshore wind projects with an aim to have 5 to 6 GW of capacity developed by 2028 and 40 GW by 2050. Grid connection cost of new projects are currently paid by the transmission system operator (TSO).
- **Potential partners:** We identified suitable 12 market players who are currently building and bidding for offshore projects in France and others have shown interest to develop offshore wind projects in France. They could be considered as potential contract parties.
- **Reduced risk on green accountability:** Latest EU regulation⁹ suggests that there could be a risk that green power produced in a different location today would not be considered green in the future. Sourcing renewable energy from France would help mitigating that risk.
- **Reduced financial risks:** Procuring energy in another country – possible through a Virtual Power Purchase Agreement (VPPA) – would increase financial risks, as CERN would bear the decorrelation risk between both markets: a VPPA would guarantee a fixed price against the local market, while CERN would still need to secure physical power supply in France.

The situation could evolve regarding available seabed and support from the government (e.g., the grid connection costs paid by the TSO). Postponing a market test and procurement plan could put the potential advantage of the current situation at risk.

We recommend to study further in detail the location of offshore wind *within* France and to develop the best match of the supply and load characteristics, because the generation profile could vary between different locations in France – e.g., between the Mediterranean, English Channel, and Atlantic areas, and even within each of the three areas.

⁹ the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources : <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L2001&from=EN>

4 Societal impacts

By procuring green energy for the FCC, CERN would support:

- **Economic development of regions where infrastructure would be built:** Developing new power production capacity has a positive impact on the local economy through direct and indirect employment, local consumptions of the employees and their families as well as additional revenue for public entities that can be reinvested in new infrastructures (e.g., school, hospitals), creating sustained GDP growth. A first estimation indicates that the total GDP impact could be around EUR 700 mn, including around 8'000 jobs¹⁰.
- **The energy transition in Europe:** Electrification of, e.g., transportation and industrial processes, is one of the main ways of achieving net zero in Europe. It will require additional new renewable capacity of 84 GW by 2030. CERN's supporting additional capacity would contribute towards achieving this objective. Moreover, procuring green energy would avoid more than 3 million t CO₂e emission¹¹ for the 15 years of FCC-ee operations.
- **Technology advancement:** Considering long-duration energy storage solutions using batteries, flow batteries and thermal storage¹² would further support the energy transition, by
 - providing the flexibility to the grid that is needed to support the RES increase,
 - reduce market exposure risk and thus lower the per MWh cost and
 - stimulate the development of technologies that are not yet widely used today.

¹⁰ Estimation made for a 500 MW project based on estimate of 15 k jobs / GW and 1.3 EUR bn /GW from <https://winddenmark.dk/sites/winddenmark.dk/files/media/document/Technical%20report-Socioeconomic%20impacts%20of%20offshore%20wind-01.07.2020.pdf>

¹¹ 31 TWh emitting 101 g CO₂e g/kWh based on 2022 average emission for power in the French grid accounting for import/export with neighboring countries (<https://app.electricitymaps.com/zone/FR>)

¹² Example for an integrated system: https://www.netl.doe.gov/sites/default/files/2020-02/TMCES/Stefan%20Niederhauser%20MAN_ETES_TMCES_Workshop_2020_v0.2.pdf

5 Next steps

There are two approaches as next steps:

A: Initiating discussions directly with offshore wind developers

There are about 10 offshore wind developers who have expressed the intent to develop offshore wind in France. We recommend approaching these developers as soon as possible to develop and test the ideas outlined in this report, better understand their interests, and refine a potential tendering approach. This “market test study” is non-committing and should be completed within one year and no later than 2030 to expect the project to produce power by the time FCC-ee operation would start in 2045. Specific objectives would be to:

- If RES capacities should be built up, identify the concrete development opportunities that could come into question for start of power generation in 2045.
- Outline what the commercial structure could be (e.g., ability to secure a fix price PPA vs. PPA with inflation index).
- Explore the interest and ability of the supplier to also provide storage as part of the PPA and potentially take over the “profile risk”.

B: Through notified national government agencies

CERN could consider obtaining an option from France for the development of a dedicated seabed by a contractual partner – seabed would be an in-kind contribution to the developer providing that power would be contracted by CERN (at least up to CERN’s need) at a lowered prize level that considers the granted seabed rights. Set up a bidding process in cooperation with either national services or international funding support agencies for such a scenario.

By obtaining first a dedicated seabed and organizing a tender, the process would be more competitive, leading to better conditions, including on the price that CERN would pay for the power produced.

This option would make the project more attractive for the FCC host states, as it would create significant value for society given that project would be expected to be larger than strictly required for CERN’s need.

This would require support from notified bodies and wind-farm developers in identifying the most attractive and feasible locations. It would also require committed support from host state authorities for such undertaking, and clarification on the conditions before entering into a bidding process.

In the meantime, CERN should independently start contacting offshore developers to test the concepts and get a preliminary sense of technical requirements and options.